

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE EXPERIENCES OF FAMILY MEMBERS OF INDIVIDUALS WITH ALCOHOL DEPENDENCE IN SELF-HELP GROUPS

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Abstract

This study explores the experiences of family members of individuals with alcohol dependence who participate in self-help groups. A qualitative research design was employed, utilizing semi-structured interviews and content analysis with eight participants from self-help groups in the Western region of Lithuania. The findings indicate that participation in self-help groups provides emotional support, reduces feelings of isolation, and fosters self-confidence and personal development. Moreover, these groups were found to enhance coping strategies, strengthen emotional resilience, and facilitate a deeper understanding of addiction. The results suggest that self-help groups play a crucial role in addressing the psychosocial needs of affected family members and should be integrated into broader addiction support systems.

Keywords: family members of individuals with alcohol dependence, self-help group, experiences.

Research Relevance. The harmful habits and addictions of one or more family members can have serious consequences for the entire family system, creating a tense and unhealthy home environment. A family member struggling with alcohol dependence may unintentionally cause significant harm to their loved ones, as their behavior is often unpredictable and difficult to manage. These situations often lead to emotional, physical, and psychological trauma among family members, making support essential for processing and healing from these adverse experiences (1). There is a growing recognition (2) that relatives of individuals with alcohol dependence often need to summon considerable courage, inner strength, and hope to begin attending self-help groups. Many of them feel helpless and overwhelmed by the situation. Previous experiences of disappointment or failure may lead to skepticism regarding the effectiveness of such groups, diminishing their belief in the possibility of meaningful change. In addition, family members may perceive seeking help as shameful or stigmatizing (3). Such perceptions can distort their understanding of the importance of receiving support, creating internal barriers to reaching out to professionals or peer support networks. These networks could provide not only practical help, but also emotional validation and understanding from others facing similar challenges. The resulting sense of shame can contribute to psychological distress and hinder the resolution of psychosocial problems. Ultimately, this becomes a psychological obstacle to accepting available help and engaging in the healing process.

Research Problem. While most research on addiction and its impact focuses on treatment programs or medical assistance for individuals with substance use disorders, considerably less attention is given to the well-being and emotional resilience of their family members - particularly within the context of self-help groups. Studies indicate that family members of individuals with addiction often experience symptoms of *codependency*, which can significantly impair their emotional well-being (4). Although various self-help

groups exist, their impact, effectiveness, and the experiences of participants vary depending on the group's structure, methods used, and the individual expectations of its members (5). Consequently, recent studies (6, 7, 8) emphasize the need to explore the experiences of family members in self-help groups more thoroughly, taking into account differences in their level of engagement, the behavioral impact of the addicted individual on relatives, and selecting participants who are close family members of individuals with alcohol dependence. These considerations shaped the scope of the current study and directed attention to the lived experiences of family members participating in self-help groups, with a particular focus on how such involvement influences their personal well-being.

Methodology. Research Methods. A qualitative study was conducted using semi-structured interviews, which allowed participants to share their experiences, perceptions, evaluations, and opinions. Prior to the interviews, the researchers reviewed the main themes to be discussed and identified key questions for each topic. During the interviews, the structure of the interview guide remained flexible and was adapted to the natural flow of the conversation. The sequence and wording of questions were adjusted as needed, and additional questions were asked when appropriate. Introductory and concluding questions were also used, although they were excluded from the subsequent data analysis. The study was carried out in accordance with ethical research principles and without infringing upon participants' rights. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study, the data collection methods, and their right to privacy. They were also informed of their right to decline to answer any interview question. Throughout the research process, efforts were made to create a safe and trusting environment by ensuring participant anonymity and confidentiality. To protect participants' identities, pseudonyms were replaced with numerical codes.

Data Analysis Method. Content analysis was selected as the methodological approach for this study

due to its systematic framework for interpreting data obtained through semi-structured interviews. This method enables the identification of “key” words and their classification into categories and subcategories. The findings are then quantitatively assessed and integrated into the broader context of the phenomenon under investigation, with a focus on describing their content.

Sample Description. A purposive sampling strategy was used, meaning that participants were selected based on the criterion that they have a close relative with alcohol dependence. The participants were chosen according to the following criteria: (1) individuals whose spouse has a medically diagnosed alcohol use disorder; (2) individuals who are currently participating in self-help groups; (3) individuals whose participation in self-help groups has lasted no less than six months.

The study involved participants from the Western region of Lithuania. The sampling process was carried out in such a way that each new case provided additional or new information, as this is essential for generating conceptual categories. The researchers continued conducting interviews until the identified categories became “saturated,” i.e., responses began to repeat. In this case, it was sufficient to interview eight participants.

Research Findings and Discussion. An analysis of the interview content revealed 11 subcategories, which were grouped into 5 broader categories: *social support*, *personal growth*, *emotional stability*, *spiritual development*, and *coping strategies*. A conceptual map was then developed, linking the subcategories and categories into a unifying theme (Figure 1), which reflects the participants' experiences and the impact of self-help groups on individual well-being.

Fig 1. The impact of self-help groups on individual well-being: a map of experiences

Social Support

Sense of Belonging. During the interviews, participants emphasized the support received from fellow group members: *You realize that these situations really do repeat themselves. One way or another, these events... well, the core of them is similar. And so you understand that you're not alone, that there are like-minded people, and somehow it becomes easier.* (3); *From the very first meeting, I understood that this was exactly the place for me, that these people are my kindred spirits who also share their experiences, and there's no shame in that, because my life had felt so closed off.* (1,2,6).

Emotional Safety. Participants also emphasized the sense of safety they experienced in the group: *I speak there, knowing that those are people just like me. I know they understand what I'm talking about, and I feel calm there.* (2); *They understand me with just half a word; sometimes it feels like we understand each other even in silence.* (4,7,8)

Personal Growth

Self-Confidence. A strong theme that emerged during the interviews was the participants' increased self-confidence: *I began to believe in myself, to trust myself. And interestingly, I became more independent. I no longer need others to validate what I think ...to tell me whether it's true or whether I'm thinking correctly. I feel like I've grown internally.* (1); *When I started attending the self-help group, my life changed significantly. I began to believe more in myself and in my abilities. I gained confidence... something I had always lacked.* (4,6,2); *I realized that I began to trust my own strength, to believe in what I was doing... I started to hold my head up high...* (5,7).

Positive Changes in Relationships. Participants also reported experiencing personal growth through improved relationships with others: *The group works I've discovered things in myself that help me focus on relationships with others. If a conflict starts, I can now restrain myself, understand myself and the other person. It's become easier to communicate with my daughter. I*

don't know exactly what changed, but I've noticed that I now freely choose my words and talk to her easily. (2); My relationships with people have only changed for the better. I can't think of a single reason to doubt that. Simply for the better, because I began to understand people differently. (3); It feels like I've grown up... especially in how I relate to my family. I'm able to listen and try to understand. (5,8).

Emotional Stability

Reduced Anxiety Levels. Participants shared experiences indicating a noticeable reduction in anxiety: ...but first of all, there's no more anxiety. Honestly, I used to be prone to depression, but when I started attending the group and following the 12-step program, I completely forgot what that even feels like. My sleep improved a lot, and naturally, my overall well-being improved too. When I feel good, I have more energy. I try to stay in the here and now, in the present moment, and just enjoy what I have. (2); My life has definitely improved. Psychologically, I can now accept more and find some answers within myself, and when I find those answers, I am able to calm down because I know how to handle things. (4).

Acceptance of Self and Others. Participants also highlighted the importance of learning to accept themselves and others: ...through the support of the group, I realized that I'm not the one causing the alcoholism—that this is his problem. But by staying together and attending the group, I can really help with the healing process and live a peaceful life. I now accept myself and have begun to understand him as well. (8, 6); It's as if I have accepted myself internally. I feel more mature and started to understand myself differently. I feel calm, more grown up, and I have forgiven my parents. (1).

Patience to Wait for the Right Moment. The ability to wait for an appropriate moment to communicate was also emphasized: "I have learned to wait for the right moment to talk. So, perhaps, this is something I gained through the group... (6, 2).

Spiritual Growth

Daily Prayer. Participants emphasized the significance of prayer in their daily lives: I pray to God, give me a healthy day today. And throughout the day, I apply the principles of the 12-step program. (1, 4, 6, 7); I have a daily prayer I say at work, and it is so unique—it helps in every situation. Especially when I really need to calm down, I recite it. (2); This daily prayer feels like a moment of peace—you focus, calm down, and I have started to find meaning and serenity through prayer. (3, 5).

Faith in God. Participants also described their personal experiences and relationship with God:...and ultimately that higher power, it feels like God arranges everything just the way it should be. (4, 5); I turn to God often. I pray that He gives me the strength to endure everything and to learn what I have yet to learn. (2); Believing in God, in the idea that everything is laid out for us from above, helps me not to break down. Sometimes I talk to Him, I ask, I give thanks and somehow it makes me feel calmer. (5).

Managing Life Situations

Conflict Resolution. Participants emphasized that attending self-help groups enabled them to better manage conflict situations: I truly noticed a change—there were many conflict situations in both my personal life and at work. What I understood through the group is that you should never let your initial emotion take over. Just wait, calm down, and then formulate your response—because that first reaction can really harm you. (4); It helps me focus on my relationships with others. If a conflict begins, it's now much easier to stay calm, understand myself, and understand the other person. (2); I've learned to accept conflict situations. I've realized that even when we argue, we can find solutions. I view conflicts—whether at home or at work, much more calmly now. (1, 5, 8).

Acceptance of Stressful Situations. Various stressful experiences that participants encountered are now approached with greater emotional resilience: I stopped banging my head against the wall, stressing out when things go wrong—especially when I don't understand why they're going wrong or why someone is behaving a certain way. (1); I stopped fighting with myself and experiencing constant anxiety and stress when things don't go the way I expected—when I don't understand why they're happening this way, and why it's happening to me. (4); I've realized that stress will always be part of life, but how I respond to it depends entirely on me. I can choose to stress and harm my health, or I can respond rationally—ask myself what I can change or simply wait for the situation to pass. (3).

The findings of this study indicate that self-help groups operate as multifaceted support systems that not only provide social and emotional assistance but also facilitate participants' emotional, psychological, and spiritual development, thereby contributing to an improved overall quality of life. Engagement in these groups was found to enhance personal well-being and to support individuals in adapting to the complex challenges associated with having a close relative suffering from alcohol dependency. A prominent theme that emerged was the significance of a sense of community. Participants emphasized that group membership helped them recognize they were not alone in confronting their difficulties. The groups provided a nonjudgmental and empathetic environment where members felt safe to openly express their experiences. This shared understanding fostered emotional security and a strong sense of belonging. Improvements in interpersonal relationships were also reported, particularly with family members. Participants described learning to communicate more openly, empathetically, and respectfully, as well as to regulate emotions more effectively during interpersonal conflicts, thereby enhancing the overall quality of their interactions. Furthermore, participation in the groups contributed to the pursuit of emotional stability. Reduced anxiety levels enhanced psychological well-being, and an improved capacity for self-soothing and present-moment awareness were commonly reported. Many participants noted that their involvement in the groups enabled them to develop a deeper understanding and acceptance of both themselves and others.

Practices of forgiveness, self-compassion, and compassion toward others emerged as key elements in their process of inner growth. The research findings are consistent with previous studies emphasizing the role of self-help groups in strengthening the internal coping resources of family members (9,10). However, the present study further underscores the significance of the spiritual dimension. Participants frequently referred to the importance of faith in God and daily prayer as sources of inner peace, hope, and existential meaning. Spiritual development emerged as a key contributor to their emotional resilience. A related study (11) demonstrated that self-help groups do not provide direct instructions on how family members should act or respond to specific situations. Instead, participants acquire insights and practical knowledge through shared experiences with other group members. This peer-based learning process enables individuals to identify personalized solutions and develop effective strategies for navigating various life challenges. The findings also indicate that participants gradually developed an enhanced ability to recognize and manage conflicts and stressful situations. They became more attuned to the role of emotions in problem-solving and reported a more rational approach to coping with life's uncertainties, which contributed to a reduction in perceived stress levels. These results suggest that self-help groups may serve not only a therapeutic but also a preventive function by mitigating the emotional risks faced by family members of individuals with substance use disorders. Accordingly, efforts should be made to increase the accessibility of such groups and to incorporate them more fully into the comprehensive system of addiction treatment and family support services.

Conclusions

The results of this study demonstrate that participants discovered a sense of belonging within self-help groups, experienced emotional safety, and felt heard and accepted without judgment. This experience has been shown to alleviate anxiety and contribute to the restoration of inner balance. The formation of supportive relationships within the groups enabled participants to move away from emotional isolation, share their personal experiences, and gain new insights about themselves and others. The provision of emotional support and the sense of group membership were identified as pivotal factors in coping with challenging circumstances and engendering hope for positive transformation.

Furthermore, it was found that self-help groups significantly contribute to participants' personal growth. Participants in the study reported developing greater self-confidence, becoming more accepting of themselves and others, forgiving their loved ones, and transforming communication patterns within the family. Participants reported learning constructive approaches to conflict resolution in a constructive manner, the recognition of their emotions, and the effective regulation of these emotions. Furthermore, the spiritual dimension exerts a significant influence on group activities. Prayer, faith in a higher power, and introspective dialogue facilitate the maintenance of hope, the pursuit

of meaning in adversity, and the cultivation of a more positive relationship with life. The aforementioned changes have been demonstrated to engender enhanced psychological well-being, fortified family relationships, and augmented overall life stability.

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